

ACADEMIA MEETS INDUSTRY EVENT 1

ARIES

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Academia meets Industry Event 1

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ABSTRACT

The ARIES WP14, Promoting Innovation, intends to ensure that technology developments inside ARIES are properly evaluated and assessed with the final aim to provide society with identified commercial applications of the supported research potential.

Relation with industry is key to coordination and joint research activities, increasing synergies between laboratories, universities, specialized institutes and applied research institutes in the consortium. This deliverable reports the 1st ARIES meets industry event, which has been dedicated to Additive Manufacturing and Advanced Technologies for Accelerator Application.

ARIES Consortium, 2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The ARIES WP14, Promoting Innovation, intends to ensure that technology developments inside ARIES are *properly evaluated and assessed* with the final aim to provide society with identified commercial applications of the supported research potential.

Relations with industry is key to coordination and joint research activities, increasing synergies between laboratories, universities, specialized institutes and applied research institutes in the consortium. For this reason, WP14 has committed to organizing two industry-academia events to bring the communities together. The first ARIES meets industry event is dedicated to Additive Manufacturing and Advanced Technologies for Accelerator Applications. This deliverable reports about this event.

1. Introduction

One of the strategic goals of ARIES is to enhance innovation in the accelerator community and developing novel concepts and technologies in the related technology sectors. This will be done by involving industry in the setting up of co-innovation programmes and in the selection and promotion of innovative technologies, while supporting the societal application of accelerators.

As one of the ways to implement the ARIES strategic platform, topical meetings among academia and industry expert are key to develop and establish the necessary network and exchange of technical information that are vital and preliminary to the development of commercial feasibility of novel concepts within accelerator science.

In this document, we describe in detail the Workshop on Additive Manufacturing that was held at the ESA Business Innovation Centre of the Wigner Research Center for Physics in Budapest, on April 8th, 2019, its aims, the participation, the main content of the presentations and of the panel discussion held.

2. Additive Manufacturing Workshop: Overview

The workshops aim was to bring together researchers from both academia, laboratories and industry, providing a platform, for the useful exchange of technical and strategical information. The day was organized around a series of specific technical presentations about the current and future opportunities and developments in Additive Manufacturing (AM), with particular reference to those that have accelerator applications, and a final panel discussion. This discussion included applications in the field of materials for superconductors, developments of processes and commonalities between accelerators technologies and other areas like aerospace and construction engineering.

Participation was free, but subject to prior registration, for logistical and security reasons (the site of the workshop was the nuclear centre of the Wigner Research Institute, In KFKI Campus where a nuclear power plan is located subject to obvious controls and safety prescriptions).

3. Organization and modality

An organizing committee was set up to oversee the preparation of the event, the technical content, identification and the selection of appropriate speakers. The Organizing Committee included CERN, STFC and MTA Wigner RCP.

The committee completed a number of teleconferences to finalize the organization of the event. Additionally some in-person meetings with partial participation were held.

The logistical aspects were taken care of by the MTA Wigner Research Centre for Physics (RCP), Konkoly-Thege Miklós street 29-33, Budapest which was hosting the event. MTA Wigner RCP also acts as headquarter of the Business Incubator Centre of the ESA.

Bus transportation to and from the hotel in the center of Budapest, where a large part of the participants to the workshop were staying, was arranged by MTA Wigner RCP.

The date of the workshop was chosen to precede the ARIES annual meeting, scheduled from April 9th to April 12th in such a way to optimize logistical resources and minimize travel time for ARIES members wanting to take part in both the events.

A web site for the event was created in November 2018, and relevant communication material was produced and circulated. Relevant information was spread out via e-mail to the ARIES mailing list as well as to the other communication channels open to the organizing committee.

For Communication and Dissemination purposes a flyer was prepared by STFC and MTA Wigner RCP together and promoted both in CERN, the other laboratories and through email communications:

**Additive Manufacturing:
Advanced Technologies for Accelerator Applications**
8 April 2019 - Budapest

ARIES WP14 - Promoting Innovation - presents an academic - industry event on Additive Manufacturing for Accelerator Applications

- Current and Future Opportunities
- AM developments in accelerator applications
- Networking opportunities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No 730871

MTA Wigner Research Centre for Physics - ESA BIC Hungary Budapest
More information, including registration can be found at:
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/775278/overview>

The web site including relevant information can be found here:
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/775278/overview>

A timetable of the event can be found from the site and below:

09:00	Registration <i>Other Institutes</i>	09:00 - 09:15
	Welcome Speech <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Maurizio Vretenar</i> 09:15 - 09:25
	Braod presentation of AM Technology <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Louise Geekie</i> 09:25 - 09:50
10:00	Overview of AM current trends, recent developments and applications in particle accelerators <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Prof. Toms Torims</i> 09:50 - 10:15
	Coffee Break <i>Other Institutes</i>	10:15 - 10:35
	AM and beamlines applications <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Chu Lun Alex Leung</i> 10:35 - 11:00
11:00	Control of the microstructure and performance requirements for superconductors <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Carmine Senatore</i> ✉ 11:00 - 11:25
	AM and RHP industrial advanced applications <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Michael Kitzmantel</i> ✉ 11:25 - 11:50
12:00	Future trends of the mosaic of AM technologies of interest to the accelerator physics applications <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Dr Frank Brückner</i> 11:50 - 12:25
	Lunch Break (Finger food)	
13:00	<i>Other Institutes</i>	12:25 - 13:15
	Interactive Session <i>Other Institutes</i>	13:15 - 14:00
14:00	Thin films for superconducting cavities and AM <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Dr Oleg Malyshev</i> ✉ 14:00 - 14:25
	3D printing for Ultra-High vacuum applications <i>Other Institutes</i>	<i>Delerue Nicolas</i> ✉ 14:25 - 15:00
15:00	Coffee Break <i>Other Institutes</i>	15:00 - 15:20
	Interactive Session - Panel Discussion <i>Other Institutes</i>	15:20 - 16:20
16:00	<i>Other Institutes</i>	

The published registered participant list (36 participants) can be accessed at:
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/775278/registrations/participants>

Having closed the registration a few days before the date of the event, late participants could not register online, and so not all participants are included in the above link. Around 40 participants in total were in attendance for all or part of the workshop.

Good by material: Printed program, textile bags, maps, T-Shirt with logos (CERN, MTA Wigner RCP, ESA BIC Hungary, Aries and workshop), pens were offered for the participants.

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4. Highlight of presentations

The list of all the presentations given on the day can be accessed at the link below, where it is also possible to download the material, which is available via open access:

<https://indico.cern.ch/event/775278/timetable/#20190408>

The day opened with an introduction and welcome from the ARIES Project Coordinator (Maurizio Vretenar), and with information about the agenda.

Péter Lévai (Director General of MTA Wigner RCP) welcomed the participants, and Zsuzsanna Tandi, WP14 partner, introduced shortly the Institute.

Louise Geekie, from the company Croft Additive Manufacturing, gave a presentation on the background and current state of additive manufacturing including her belief that “the extensive capabilities of metal 3D printing can create new opportunities for industrial processes across many industrial sectors”. She reported the example of her company, which is producing innovative filter designs and other products that cannot be manufactured conventionally. Louise showed a useful “curve of expectation” of the technology trend, indicating that we are now in a phase indicated as “plateau of production”, following the phases of peak and valleys of inflated expectation and disillusionment. Currently there is more steadily increasing demand and growth, with the aerospace and automotive industries being the largest share of the market.

Prof. Toms Torims presented an overview of the AM current trends and the way the technology is already used in the accelerator sector, with practical examples including those from the shipping industry.

Prof. Carmine Senatore showed the requirements of the microstructure for superconductor materials, presenting the starting point for any application of AM for production of superconductive material.

A very interesting presentation was given by Dr. Alex Leung, from University College London. In his presentation he demonstrated the reversed paradigm of applications: not what AM can do for accelerator technologies, but the other way around. In fact, accelerators like the DIAMOND synchrotron light source can provide a unique opportunity to investigate the process of AM in a way that could not be possible with similar precision and accuracy. Today the focus is not anymore on the topological aspects and the production of fancy geometries, but instead on the mastering of the process itself, for the production of the material characteristics that are requested by the market.

Michel Kitzmantel, from the company RHP-Technology, presented some industrial applications, and micro 3D printing of metal and ceramics. He reported on the large spectrum of possibilities opened by the combination of technologies, combining 3D printing with Metal injection molding for example, or the possibilities to 3D print materials hybrid, creating de facto new materials whose properties could be matched to specific purposes.

Other presentations not described in this report in detail showed the mosaic of the AM technologies of interest for particle accelerators, the general trend and the technological related aspects for UHV application, and for thin films for Superconductive Cavities.

5. Panel Discussion

After the presentation session, and the buffet lunch that provided a practical networking opportunity, time was reserved for a panel discussion. To facilitate the discussion a short questionnaire was distributed in the morning (included in annex A). 21 responses were collected on the day from this survey and the results are displayed below:

WHAT TYPE OF ORGANISATION DO YOU COME FROM?

RESPONSE	NUMBER
UNIVERISTY	8
INDUSTRY	3
LARGE FACILITY	4
GOVERNMENT/FUNDING ORGANISATION	6

HOW DO YOU CURRENTLY USE (OR INTEND TO USE) AM TECHNOLOGY NOW?

RESPONSE	TYPE OF RESPONDENT			
	Industry	Facility	University	Government
PROTOTYPING	1	1	2	1
EXPERIMENTING TO SEE HOW IT CAN BE APPLIED	1	3	5	3
FINAL PRODUCT MANUFACTURING	2		2	1
BUILDING PARTS THAT CANNOT BE MADE USING TRADITIONAL METHODS	3	1	4	2
NOT USING/INTENDING TO USE			3	3

WHERE DO YOU THINK THE NEXT BIG BREAKTHROUGH IN AM IS NEEDED?

INDUSTRY FACILITY UNIVERSITY GOVERNMENT

ENERGY SECTOR	2	1	5	2
MEDICAL APPLICATIONS	1	2	2	2
TRANSPORT	1	1	4	2
CUSTOM PRODUCTS	3	2	2	4
MASS PRODUCTION	1	1	2	1
OTHER-ACCELERATORS		1	1	1
OTHER- MULTI-METAL PRINTING		1		
OTHER-MULTIDISCIPLINARY			1	

WHAT ARE THE BARRIERS TO ADOPTION OF THIS TECHNOLOGY?

	INDUSTRY	FACILITY	UNIVERSITY	GOVERNMENT
EXPENSE	1	2	2	3
QUALIFICATION AND STANDARDS	3	3	4	2
LACK OF FEEDSTOCKS		1		1
NO APPLICATIONS IN INDIVIDUAL RESEARCH AREAS			1	2
DIFFICULTY IN RECRUITING EXPERTISE			2	1
MAUNUFACTURING SPEED/SIZE	1	2	2	1

THREAT TO IP RIGHTS	2
OTHER- ACCEPTANCE BY INDUSTRY	1
OTHER- LACK OF UNDERSTANDING OF PROCESS	1
OTHER- NEED TO DESIGN FOR AM	1

WHAT WILL BE THE MOST DISRUPTIVE EFFECT OF AM?

	INDUSTRY	FACILITY	UNIVERSITY	GOVERNMENT
SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION TO BOOST INDUSTRY 4.0 AND DIGITISED PRODUCTION	1	1	3	1
CIRCULAR ECONOMY	1		2	1
ACCELERATE NEW MATERIAL AND PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	2	2	3	4
INCREASED FUNCTIONALITY OF PRODUCTS	2	3	4	4
CHANGE TO CUSTOMER/SUPPLIER RELATIONSHIP				3
SUPPLY CHAINS	1			2

WILL 3D PRINTING IMPACT THE FUTURE OF ACCELERATORS AND IN WHICH SPECIFIC AREA?

	INDUSTRY	FACILITY	UNIVERSITY	GOVERNMENT
MGB ₂ AND HTS SUPERCONDUCTIVITY			1	1
NB AND LTS SUPERCONDUCTIVITY			2	
RESIN AND PLASTICS FOR ELECTRICAL INSULATIONS	1	1	2	
STRUCTURAL MATERIALS AND METALS	2	2	6	3
SPECIAL PARTS	3	3	5	4
NO IMPACT	0	0	0	0

The survey indicated that the respondents came from a mixed background as required by the objectives of WP14. Most respondents were already or are intending to use AM with the most important uses seen as the ability to build parts not possible using conventional techniques. In addition the ability of AM to make replacement parts in a short timescale, if designed with AM in mind, was seen as a key advantage that could be exploited.

The longest discussion was around barriers to adoption due to the lack of standards currently in the market seen as the key obstacle to the full exploitation. It was generally agreed that further research and working across industry and academia/ laboratories would be key to solving this issue. All participants acknowledged the potential impact of AM on accelerators. Particularly in the area of special parts hard or impossible to make using conventional methods, or structural materials and metals thought there would be future impacts with joint investigations worth pursuing.

6. Conclusion

The WP14 in the ARIES project has successfully held the first of the Academy-meets-industry event, dedicated to Additive Manufacturing and Particle Accelerators. There were almost 40 participants at the event, and it was a useful occasion to exchange technical information, to review the status of the technology, and cast an eye on the future trends of the technology and of its applications in the sector of the particle accelerators. We received many positive feedbacks from participants and speakers, reporting on the effectiveness of the day and of the new and interesting contacts they made.

Annex A**Survey****Additive Manufacturing (AM):
Advanced Technologies for Accelerator Applications
Monday 8 April 2019****What type of organisation do you come from?**

1. University
2. Industry
3. Large facility
4. Government/ funding organisation
5. Other

How do you currently use (or intend to use) AM technology now?

1. Prototyping
2. Experimenting to see how it can be applied
3. Final product manufacturing
4. Building parts that cannot be made using traditional methods
5. Not using/intending to use

Where do you think the next big breakthrough in additive manufacturing is needed?

1. Metal 3D printing for energy sector (turbines, motor,..)
2. Medical applications (dental products, implants...)
3. Vehicles / transport (aerospace and series production)
4. Custom products
5. Mass production
6. Other (please give details)

What are the barriers to adoption of this technology?

1. Expense
2. Qualification of produced parts according to different processing routes, certification (for medical approval) and standards adoption
3. Not enough feedstocks
4. No applications in your research area
5. Difficulty in recruiting expertise
6. Manufacturing speed and/or size
7. Threat to IP rights of designers and producers
8. Other (provide details)

What will be the most disruptive effect of AM?

1. Sustainable production (increased efficiency, optimized resources use)
2. The right tool to boost industry 4.0 and to digitized production
3. Circular economy (repair and remanufacturing of parts, reduce waste)
4. Accelerate new materials and products development
5. Increase functionality of products
6. Change to customer/supplier relationship (Manufacture on demand)
7. Supply chains (eliminate inventories)
8. Other (provide details)

Will 3D printing impact the future of accelerators and in which specific area? (Provide details if possible)

1. MgB₂ and HTS superconductivity.
2. Nb and LTS superconductivity
3. Resin and plastics for electrical insulations
4. Structural materials and metals
5. Special parts
6. No impact